

Authors' Response to Reviews of

Assessing the best hour to start the day: an appraisal of seasonal Daylight Saving Time

Authors: JM Martín-Olalla and Jorge Mira. Reviewers: Michael C. Antle (2) and Andrew N. Coogan (4)
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RC: *Reviewers' Comment*, AR: Authors' Response, Manuscript Text

Round 3. Dated 02 December 2024 08:30CET

Authrs' response DOI: 10.1098/RSOS.240727/V4/RESPONSE1

We thank Reviewer 2 and Reviewer 4, and the Editorial Office for the recommendation and decision to accept our revision 2 of the manuscript. We are very much pleased.

1. Changes in the third revised version

- We have amended the manuscript in line with reviewer 2's comments. See below the detailed response.
- We added six more references (numbers 18-25-50-77-103-109) that have been published recently, get to our knowledge recently or were skipped in previous revisions. We just added the references without any further context to them.
- Throughout the manuscript some usages of the phrase "medical associations" have changed into "sleep associations".
- In section 2, we added "mean solar time" in two usages of time.
- In section 5, one sentence was amended for the sake of clarity.
- In section 8, one sentence was amended.

2. Brief response to reviewer 2

Reviewer's comment DOI: 10.1098/RSOS.240727/V2/REVIEW1 Reviewer 2 is Michael C. Antle

RC: 1. page 3. *"fundamental" not "foundamental"*.

AR: We thank immensely the through editing by reviewer 2 and apologize once more for our mistakes. The manuscript was amended in line with this comment.

RC: 2. Page 7. *The sentence "Schools, universities, appointments, usually start at 7am or at 8am, or any other whole hour." might be true for where the authors live, but this is not universally true. Many schools,*

universities and businesses start their class or appointment schedules at time other than the full hour (my children in public school start their day at 8:46; the shifts for health care staff at our nearby hospital start at 6:45, and many businesses in my community open on the half hour). In any case, this does not appear to be central to the authors point, which can probably be made just as effectively without specifying particular start times.

AR: Thank you very much for this comment.

The sentence was removed in revision 3. We agree it added little to our point.

Nonetheless we take this opportunity to stress the word “usually” in our sentence. Daily rhythms provided by time use surveys are evidence that whole hours are preferred, followed by half whole hours. This does not exclude other specific start times, which indeed may be becoming more convenient as a way to circumvent issues related to public transportation and road traffic. Both benefit from uniform rates of usage, compared to discrete rates.

References